

EcoGPX®: a Digital Tool Rooted in People and Place

Primary Contributor: Dr. Alex Boyd Additional contributors: Dr Jo Scott
Dr Ben Spatz
Project Members: Arielle Bennett

14 July 2025

Intercultural Roots for Public Health is a UK-registered charity working at the intersection of arts, health, and environmental awareness. With a mission to support community wellbeing and positive social change, the organisation coordinates creative and educational projects through a diverse network of over 800 artists, practitioners, scholars and teachers across 50+ countries around the world. A key innovation in recent years has been the development of EcoGPX®, a suite of digital and place-based protocols, frameworks and tools (including a social media app, PLACES by EcoGPX®, described later in this case study) funded by Innovate UK and designed to cultivate ecological and social engagement through arts-led interventions. Through participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, the Intercultural Roots and newly incorporated EcoGPX Ltd team is exploring how the use of immersive extended reality (XR) technologies (such as augmented reality, virtual reality and spatial audio) and artificial intelligence (AI) might enhance or undermine the organisation's community-focused goals, values, and principles.

This case study draws on insights from Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd team members Dr Alex Boyd, Dr Jo Scott, and Dr Ben Spatz to examine their current work, the ethical dilemmas posed by emerging technologies, and their aspirations for responsible innovation.

Building Technology from the Ground Up

The EcoGPX project emerged from a lineage of community-embedded initiatives run by Intercultural Roots that invited participants to reflect on what matters to them in the places they inhabit. These initiatives laid the groundwork for PLACES by EcoGPX®, an ethical social media mobile app developed and tested through bottom-up iterative design and eco-arts residencies in collaboration with local communities in Ilkley-Bradford and Coventry, UK. Rather than starting with a technological agenda, the team approached process development with deep listening and place-based engagement.

This involved being with communities in the places where they live, work and gather in order to understand what matters to them and how place-based creative practices can address identified issues and challenges. This initial 'rooting' phase led to a series of residencies with local artists through which a range of creative practices were shared and the primary principles and affordances of the app were developed. The evaluation of the Coventry project identified that these approaches support the development of new and mutually beneficial connections between people and places, as well as changing how places are seen and valued, positively impacting on participants' wellbeing,

self-esteem and confidence.

The app itself helps people explore and reflect on their local environment through creative prompts, stories and soundscapes. For participants it encourages interactive engagement with place-based content designed to support wellbeing and connection to nature, and for contributors, the opportunity to create their own or respond to other people's place-based media as a locally crowd-sourced ripple effect. The design and functioning of the Places app are underpinned by regenerative principles and practices, as well as critical research on how dominant ways of using technology can be transformed by a deeper understanding of embodiment and emplacement. The team envisions using technologies to nourish, connect and share, rather than to extract and exploit. With this goal in mind, the PLACES app uses a grounded geolocated algorithmic structure to connect and reconnect users to places and people, rather than aiming to maximise time on the app (as many commercial social media platforms do).

Jo, who is Quality Monitoring and Evaluation Consultant for EcoGPX Ltd, explains: "What's important is that technology isn't imposed on a community, but co-created with them. The app is a tool for amplifying the practices and knowledge already held in those places." This participatory approach helped ensure that the app's features reflect local needs – particularly in relation to wellbeing, social connection, and access to green and blue spaces. The Coventry experience, building on earlier experiences in the Bradford area, reinforced the team's commitment to accessibility, inclusivity and ethical design – principles that continue to guide their work. Those same principles will be taken into the development of the next proposed app in the suite: MEMORIES by EcoGPX®. The new app aims to support people living with dementia, and their carers, family and friends, by combining personalised therapeutic media with the potential for the integration of AI and LLMs if ethical utilisation and privacy can be ensured.

Ben, EcoGPX Ltd's Creative Director, adds: "Through this approach, we're asking fundamental questions: who is the technology for, and what assumptions are built into its design? We're not interested in replicating top-down or exploitative models. Instead, we're exploring what it means to develop technology that serves the community rather than extracts from it."

Ethical Challenges in the AI Landscape

A core tension for Intercultural Roots is the potential role of AI in its work. While the team is keen to explore how AI might enhance and streamline areas such as memory curation or matching collaborators across networks, they are also cognisant of the ethical issues surrounding the use of this technology. For instance, as part of the proposed Memories app, an AI / LLM model could be developed and trained on datasets gathered by an individual's family, composed of sounds, texts, images or video footage that represent and record special memories and connections through their lives. Such datasets could then be collaboratively curated with the help of machine learning and in partnership with families and carers to offer an individual with a dementia diagnosis a set of immersive reminiscence experiences, which trace gentle routes back into their life experiences and relationships.

In this type of AI deployment, data privacy is clearly paramount and would need careful and sensitive management – in contrast to the way in which current commercial models are making use of creative content. As Alex, the founder of Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd, says: "AI brings up a lot of ethical concerns for our community of artists and practitioners. There are deep concerns around

data extraction, valuing artist’s IP, and consent. Our online use of a single AI-generated image caused someone to leave our Arts Disability Network, which really hammered home the sensitivities and emotion around this subject.”

Jo, meanwhile, highlights the ecological and human impact of AI: “We have to ask if the energy and water use of large-scale AI systems is justified by what they offer. Can AI implementation and usage ever be climate-conscious? And we must also recognise that AI isn’t truly artificial – there is invisible pre- and post-algorithmic human labour behind the technology, in the form of content moderators, data annotators and so on. These people are often exploited, working in precarious conditions.”

Another area of concern for the Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd team – brought to the fore through their participation in the Practitioners Hub – is the perceived limitations of existing AI ethics frameworks. These frameworks, they believe, tend to focus narrowly on technical compliance or abstract ethical concepts, to the exclusion of the deeper structural issues that lie behind technological development, such as power dynamics, labour conditions, environmental impact, lived experiences, and economic models. Ben says: “What often gets called ‘ethics’ in AI is very limited. It doesn’t question the political economy of AI, the assumptions it carries, or the way it structures relationships. For Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd, true ethics means asking difficult questions about who benefits, who is harmed, and what kind of technological futures we want to build. We are trying to design tools that don’t hook people into extractive systems.”

Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has helped the Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd team to deepen their critical engagement with AI, giving them space to reflect on real-world risks and values-based design approaches. “The Hub gave us language and frameworks to articulate concerns we were already feeling,” says Alex. “It allowed us to learn from people in very different sectors, but facing similar ethical dilemmas, and to witness that the financial lure of sponsorship from big tech can sometimes silence ethical dissent”.

Next Steps: Exploring Positive Use Cases

Despite these concerns, Intercultural Roots is not anti-technology. In fact, the team is actively exploring ways to use digital tools ethically and inclusively. Their current project, Extending Nature, funded by Innovate UK’s Mindset-XR programme, enhances the PLACES by EcoGPX[®] app to support people with Generalised Anxiety Disorder (GAD).

Mindset-XR seeks to revolutionise digital mental health by backing innovative technologies aligned with NHS England’s needs. GAD affects over 3 million UK adults and contributes to £100 billion in annual economic losses – including £45 billion from stress-related workplace absence alone. Traditional therapeutic access is often limited and costly, with sessions averaging £60 per hour, and many individuals never receive treatment.

Extending Nature uses cutting-edge XR to deliver affordable, place-based therapeutic support via the Places by EcoGPX[®] mobile app and a new, secure web-based portal for referrals. It empowers users to engage in immersive ‘ecosomatic’ practices, such as breathwork, grounding, and nature visualisation, through spatialised sound, 360° video, and AR/VR guidance. These digital experiences are tailored to support health-seeking behaviours and offer clinically aligned, self-guided interventions suitable for Step 2 of NHS England’s care model.

Developed in co-creation with artists and individuals with lived experience of GAD, the app turns everyday green and blue spaces into restorative environments. Users can explore personalised journeys, access pre-recorded sessions from expert international ecosomatic practitioners, and leave their own geolocated responses – transforming local landscapes into shared, therapeutic digital ecosystems. Designed with clinical oversight, accessibility and equity at its core, Extending Nature offers scalable, inclusive mental health support that connects people more deeply to place, community and nature – wherever they are.

Jo says: "It's a therapeutic tool that reconnects people with their local ecosystems through engagement with real places, rather than with synthetic representations of distant or idealised natural spaces. Accessibility is built in from the start, not bolted on later, and content is developed collaboratively with communities."

Similarly, as mentioned earlier, MEMORIES by EcoGPX[®] is set to feature greater AI and machine learning integration, including functionality for family members to upload media that AI helps organise into reminiscence journeys for people living with Alzheimer's disease or other types of dementia.

Ben adds: "We want to build slowly, carefully, and with integrity. There's a lot of pressure to chase the latest tech trend, but we're more interested in doing what's meaningful and sustainable for our communities."

Independently evaluated EcoGPX[®] impact reports:

- UK Creative Catalyst Award 2023-24 £49,970 - 'EcoGPX[®]' - [Independent evaluation report](#).
- Innovate UK Launchpad: immersive & creative 2024 £100,000 - 'EcoGPX[®] Launchpad Coventry and Warwickshire' - [Full impact report](#) and [Visual report](#).

Contact:

Intercultural Roots for Public Health - [Contact us](#) | [Charitable donation](#)

EcoGPX Ltd - <https://ecogpx.com/>

Key Takeaways

- EcoGPX[®] tools are co-created with local communities to ensure digital interventions reflect real needs and lived experiences.
- AI is only integrated into EcoGPX[®] projects through a careful process that prioritises ethical oversight, consent and data privacy.
- The Intercultural Roots and EcoGPX Ltd team challenges narrow AI ethics frameworks, calling for deeper attention to power, labour, and environmental impact.
- Projects such as Extending Nature and MEMORIES by EcoGPX[®] will explore how AI and immersive tech can support wellbeing and care.
- EcoGPX[®] prioritises slow, responsible innovation, and in some cases older or simple technologies, over fast-paced, trend-driven development, focusing on long-term community benefit and sustainability.

- Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub helped the team articulate its concerns and imagine what might constitute a values-led approach to AI.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Alex Boyd

Dr. Alex Boyd (Cert Ed, PhD, FRSA) is the Founding Executive Director of Intercultural Roots, an organization dedicated to promoting interdisciplinary collaboration rooted in equity, respect, and mutual benefit. Alex has a background in computing and systems engineering, with extensive work in community-applied arts and embodied research. He is a co-founder of the Embodied Research Working Group at the International Federation for Theatre Research and has earned his PhD from the University of California, Davis. His work has helped secure over £8M in not-for-profit funding, and his research focuses on the sustainability of traditional knowledge systems.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Ben Spatz

Ben Spatz (they/he) is a scholar-practitioner working at the intersections of artistic research and critical theories of embodiment and identity. They are the author of "Race and the Forms of Knowledge: Technique, Identity, and Place in Artistic Research" (forthcoming in 2024) and the founding editor of the videographic Journal of Embodied Research. Ben currently teaches at the University of Huddersfield and will be a Visiting Scholar at the University of Oxford during 2024–2025.

Practitioners Hub Testimonial

"Being part of The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has given us invaluable space to reflect, recalibrate, and responsibly reimagine the role of AI and immersive tech in our work. As artists, researchers and technologists embedded in communities, we often lack the language or frameworks to fully interrogate the ethical risks of emerging technologies. The Hub not only deepened our understanding, but helped validate our instinct to prioritise care, co-creation and inclusion – rather than efficiency, scale or novelty. It's helped us feel less isolated in our critical stance and more aligned with a global movement towards values-led and regenerative design."

"Through mentoring, peer exchange and provocations from leading thinkers, the Hub offered a vital counterbalance to the pressure of tech trends. It affirmed our commitment to designing regenerative ecosystems that serve communities first, and equipped us with tools to push back against extractive AI logics. We're building technologies from the ground up – rooted in people, place and purpose – and The Turing Way has been instrumental in helping us do that with clarity, courage and care."

– **Dr Alex Boyd, Intercultural Roots for Public Health & EcoGPX Ltd**

Acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub 2024-25 Cohort - case study series. *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2024, *The Turing Way* team welcomed **Alex Boyd**, and **Ben Spatz**, as Experts in Residence to represent interests and opportunities in community wellbeing and the environment. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

This work is supported by **Innovate UK BridgeAI**. The Practitioners Hub has also received funding and support from the Ecosystem Leadership Award under the EPSRC Grant EP/X03870X/1 & **The Alan Turing Institute**.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2024-25 Cohort was co-delivered by Dr **Malvika Sharan**, Senior Researcher - Open Research and **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

Cite this publication:

Boyd, A., Spatz, B., Scott, J. (2025). EcoGPX®: a Digital Tool Rooted in People and Place. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15882525>